

EVOLUTION PRECONDITIONS FOR APPEARING PHILOSOPHICALLY INCLINED LITERATURE AND ITS MAIN REPRESENTATIVE

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Abstract:

In this article, we will explore the main representatives of literature with philosophical generalizations and evolution preconditions for the emerging of the genre – philosophical prose. It is true that research about philosophical tendencies in contemporary American literature has progressed tremendously in the past two decades due to the advent and accessibility of new technologies and experiments that enable data sharing, analyzing and using for the future investigations. Consequently, it might be difficult to find a topic about which nothing is known or no literature is available. However, there is still a lot of scope for progress. Surely, we tried to do an effort while finding good and sufficient literature. Of course, making our research based only on literature, which already was thoroughly investigated, will not make our work more reliable. Therefore, when we made our research, we have noticed in the literature review that some novels of American literature with philosophical inclination are not included in scientists' works of this aspect. For sure, in our collected data we have observed works that were written in the style of existentialism. In addition, we will include sufficient information about objectivism and other comparatively new literary trends.

Key words: philosophical fiction, philosophical prose, philosophical tendencies, historical-literary comprehension, philosophical principle, artistic imagery, post-war literature, Existentialism, philosophical coating.

Introduction:

Of course, the topics of philosophical fiction have been discussed not only in the works of English or American authors, but also in the works of Russian researchers. It is worth to mention the famous work “Philosophical prose as a phenomenon of Russian classical literature” by Russian author Eremeyev A.E written in the last decade of the 20th century. In his work he states the importance of the problems of theoretical and historical-literary comprehension of the philosophical layer in Russian classical and modern literature and its' popularity throughout the world. Eremeyev concludes that

the question of the origins of philosophical prose is extremely significant. He says that studying it in the inseparability of the theoretical and historical-literary aspects makes it possible to enrich the understanding of the process of the formation of philosophical potential, as well as outline the prospects for the study of successive ties in the work of modern writers.⁶

If we speak about philosophical tendencies that were depicted by Russian scholars we can reveal two different sources of philosophical literature. The reason for one of them is the synthetic nature of artistic activity in general, connecting the spiritual and the practical, consciousness and being. The reason for the second is the intellectual and logical principle in the word as the material of literature. These two points would already be enough for different individual modifications of philosophical literature to exist, not to mention the penetration of philosophical problems into the literature of different eras.

However, in the very method of artistic assimilation of reality in literature there is a sphere that reflects the interaction of the cognitive (philosophical) and ethical moments. It is associated with the concept of the artistic content of a literary work. Bakhtin defined the concept of artistic content as follows: "The reality of cognition and ethical action, which, in its recognition and appreciation, enters the aesthetic object and undergoes here a specific intuitive unification, individuation, concretization, isolation and completion, that is, comprehensive decoration with the help of a certain material, we ... call the content of a work of art"⁷ This quote was stated by the Russian literary critique Kojinov V.V .

Another author Paliyevskiy P.V considers that the moment of cognitive cognition accompanies the activity of artistic creativity and contemplation everywhere, but in most cases it is completely inseparable from the ethical moment and cannot be expressed by an adequate judgment .⁸

The author Rodnyanskaya acknowledges that even without being highlighted, the philosophical and cognitive moment in a work can contribute to serious discoveries in comprehending the essence of phenomena: "This inner illumination of an aesthetic object in the field of verbal creativity from the degree of knowledge can rise to the degree of certain knowledge and deep comprehensions that can be highlighted by aesthetic analysis" .[five] It is important not just to single out the cognitive

⁶ "Philosophical prose as a phenomenon of Russian classical literature" by author Eremeyev A.E., RussiaЖурналФундаментальные исследования. – 2005. – № 4 – С. 19-23Филологические науки р.19–23

⁷ Кожин В.В. Происхождение романа. - М., 1963. - С.408.

⁸ Палиевский П.В. Внутренняя структура образа //Теория литературы: Основные проблемы в историческом освещении. - М., 1962.

(philosophical) and ethical aspects in the composition of the artistic content, but to indicate that the way they are connected in the artistic content may be different.⁹

So, philosophical prose is, first of all, fictional prose, if we understand artistry as “the inner quality of aesthetic phenomena that are different from other phenomena of life and cultural creativity,” and this quality has the character of an organic unity, similar to the biological creativity of life.

The epithet ‘philosophical’ indicates not only the presence of a specially highlighted theoretical philosophical principle in the composition of the artistic content, but mainly the special nature of the connection between the cognitive moment and the ethical one, a special way of artistic design, the synthesis of such principles. Different proportions of the philosophical principle, different types of connections of synthesized elements in the composition of such prose, different directions of the author’s consciousness and special ways of its embodiment - all this should help to single out the types of philosophical prose.¹⁰

The intensification of philosophical tendencies in prose falls on the era of its formation. In the second quarter of the nineteenth century, the main types of prose took shape in Russian literature. It is not surprising that, along with the forms of didactic-allegorical narration, there are varieties of philosophical journalism, aesthetics, criticism, as well as fictional prose itself with an emphasized philosophical principle based on anecdote, myth, maxim and other oral genres. In the article “The philosophical tendency in contemporary literature” Valentina Ivashova enlisted Russian authors who tended to reflect philosophically in their piece of writing. They are: Leonov (“The Russian forest”), Vladimir Tendrykov (“A topsy-turvi spring”, “Graduation night”), Yuriy Bondarev (“The shore”).

Different genre genesis determines a lot in Russian philosophical prose. So, there are examples of openly experimental prose, in which the philosophical principle is artificially introduced and gives the impression of an undissolved logical structure in the artistic fabric of a work, or a figurative illustration, an example for some author’s thesis.¹¹

Philosophical prose presupposes not so much the embodiment of the self-development of life mediated by pictures, the depiction of phenomena, as in purely artistic prose, but rather a direct, concentrated expression of the meaning of what is happening, taking place in the process of obtaining it. Moreover, the ways of thinking about the world, the paths along which thought moves, become a special subject of

⁹ Роднянская И.В. Художественность //Краткая литературная энциклопедия. - М., 1975.

¹⁰ Роднянская И.В. Художественность // Краткая литературная энциклопедия. М., 1975. Т. 8. 10. Стб. 339.

¹¹ Кожин В.В. Немецкая классическая эстетика и русская литература // Традиция в истории культуры. М., 1978. - С.193

philosophical prose. Often, works of philosophical prose are built on the primacy of a moral and philosophical thesis that is clear to the author, and the narrative is subordinated to the logic of its disclosure.

In such works, thought subordinates to itself the development of artistic imagery, or rather, is a kind of dominant that organizes the internal structure of an artistic image. It must be remembered that the supremacy of conceptual thought in the composition of an artistic image is only a tendency, a kind of semantic pole that is never attainable in practice. In a word, philosophical imagery manifests itself on the basis of concentration, consolidation of the general meaning of phenomena, as well as due to an increase in the proportion of the protagonist (heroes), the consciousness of the narrating subject. His biography includes absolutely all significant events occurring within the framework of the social whole of which he is a member. The direction of the author's consciousness in works of philosophical prose is always clearly deductive, the general meaning is often given and is only refined, proved, concretized in the process of unfolding the artistic image.¹²

Philosophical prose is also a holistic exploration of the world; but the prism through which the artist looks at the world is not a fact, not a phenomenon, but the dynamics of social consciousness, recreated in its individual contradictory forms. The narrative in philosophical prose is not the "direct embodiment of artistic thoughts" of the author, because such self-expression would be analogous to the abstract contemplation of abstract thinking. Philosophical prose is a phenomenon of art, and therefore combines knowledge and action. The author of philosophical prose does not so much form his thoughts about the world as he reveals the general state of reality, exploring the dynamics of social consciousness.¹³

In addition, it is inevitably to mention the works of other scholars and literary critiques who researched the philosophically inclined literature of America. One of the most important and initial works in this field of study is the creation of the Russian scholar Valentina Ivashova. Scientist Valentina Ivashova mentioned the notion and the preconditions of the philosophically inclined literature in her work "On the threshold of the twenty first century". Mainly, in her work she illustrates the main representatives of English, American and Russian writers, such as *Robert Penn Warren*, John Gardner, Elia Kazan and Kurt Vonnegut William Clark Styron and Saul Bellow, who wrote their literary works with philosophical coating. Mostly, we will discuss these writers in the next chapter of our dissertation paper.

Another Russian candidate of philological sciences is Novikova Irina. Her work "Philosophical tendencies in the novel of the United States of the 70s (R. Penn Warren,

¹² Кожин В.В. Происхождение романа. М., 1963. - С.408.

¹³ Кожин В.В. Происхождение романа. М., 1963. - С.408.

W. Styron, J. Gardner)” was published in 1985, in Moscow. At the beginning of her dissertation paper, she focuses on the preconditions of the genre of literature with the philosophical generalization. Her research depicts that in the 20th century, with its extraordinary dynamism of events, the period after the Second World War, nevertheless, is distinguished by the acceleration of the pace of social and scientific development. The nature of the movement of modern history has significantly expanded the range of topics offered to literature - the forms of artistic reflection have also changed, the framework of the usual literary genres has expanded. Modern literature required new ways of philosophical comprehension of the age-old problems of being and man.

Western literature of the post-war decades is permeated with mistrust of the active principle of a man. The Soviet translator L. Ginzburg gave a remarkable assessment of this change in the mood of the post-war generations: “Every person suddenly realized with special acuteness the truth that he is not free, that everything depends not on himself, but on the will of other people: any step, any, the most an insignificant act. I do not determine what to do now, where to go, what to eat. ” In an atmosphere of confusion in front of such a rapidly and imperceptibly changed being, philosophical systems imbued with the spirit of pessimism, especially existentialism, became popular among writers.

Here, it is worth to clarify that Existentialism picked up and developed the characteristic features of the tragic worldview of the Western intelligentsia, aggravated by the tragedy of the Second World War. Existentialism was widely reflected in the post-war literature of France, Germany, USA, Great Britain. The works of J.-P. Sartre and A. Camus acted as a philosophical-artist hanged the concept of existentialism. Existentialist themes, categories, ideas determined the artistic content of A. Murdoch’s philosophical novels up to her revision of her philosophical views and an appeal to Plato’s ethics. The "Sartro Orientation" was inherent in the first philosophical novels of W. Golding.¹⁴

According to Irina Novikova the emergence of philosophically inclined literature appears firstly in Europe, in such countries as France, Italy, Germany and England. The genre of the philosophical parable novel was developed in the postwar literatures of Italy, France, and the Federal Republic of Germany. In Italy, this genre is represented by the works of such famous authors as I. Calvino, G. Piovene, G. Saviane.

¹⁴ Literary criticism Literature of the peoples of Europe, America and Australiadissertation abstract in philology, specialty HAC RF 10.01.05dissertation on the topic:Philosophical tendencies in the novel of the United States of the 70s (R. Penn Warren, W. Styron, J. Gardner)Year: 1985Author of scientific work: Novikova, Irina IvanovnaAcademic degree: candidate of philological sciencesPlace of thesis defense: MoscowVAK specialty code: 10.01.05

Italo Calvino is the creator of the genre of moral and philosophical parables in post-war Italian prose. The writer is interested in ethical problems that require urgent solutions in the conditions of scientific and technological progress (his historical trilogy "The Cut Viscount" (visconte dimezzato) 1952, "The Baron on the Tree" - 1957, "The Non-Existent Knight" - (Il cavaliere inesistente 1959 should be highlighted).

The philosophical novel of France is vividly represented by the works of Vercort "People or animals? – (tes animaux denatures), 1952, Robert Merle ("Reasonable animal" - "Un animal doué de raison", 1968, "Madrapur" - VMadrapour", 1976. These writers stand out for the philosophical optimism in their books, no matter what genre they appear in and no matter what general philosophical issues they touch.

William Burrows, a modernist writer claiming the philosophical conceptuality of his work, in one of his last books "Port of Saints" of 1981 directly calls the human mind a "shell" behind which base instincts are hidden, an animal hides. W. Golding adheres to approximately the same position: "In my books I try to discover the defects of society based on the defects of human nature." The writer seeks to reveal the "defects" of man in his philosophical novels "The Lords of the Flies, 1959, "The Spire" (1964), "The Pyramid", 1967, "Free Fall, 1968.

Philosophical novels-allegories of the French novelist Le Clezio are permeated with the artist's disbelief in the spiritual forces of man (novels "The Flood" - "Le De'luge", 1966, "Terra Amata" - Terra Amata", 1967, "War" - "La Guerrd1,1970). The world in which the heroes of Le Clésio live - ".une harmonie proprement monstrueuse. The basis of the writer's philosophical novels is the idea of cataclysm as the basis of man and being, and destruction is already inherent in people.

So, in the general picture of the post-war historical and literary process, a novel stands out, built on the basis of some philosophical system, such as the "pre-Platonic" work of Murdoch (her novels "Under the Net", 1953, "The Plight from Enchanter", 1956, "The Unicorn, 1963).

As we know, literature with a philosophical tendency comes to the fore during the periods of historical changes, when, before the eyes of one or two generations, there is a breakdown in views - on society, on the role of an individual and people, on the national past of their people. It is at such frontiers, when it is difficult to understand a multitude of phenomena and find the main direction of development, that "the novel philosophizes." (Yu. Surovtsev) and begins to appear as a definite literary tendency. Two global wars and the third priery, the scientific and technological revolution, the change in the nature of public life and many other factors have led to the growing need for modern writers in the epoch-making analysis of reality. Indeed, the cataclysms of the 20th century forced writers to think about what a man is, what Good and Evil are,

but already relying on achievements in all spheres of human activity throughout many centuries of civilization, on a long historical experience. The nature of philosophical generalization, a feature inherent in the literature of a philosophical trend, has changed.

Methods:

Holistic and philosophical approaches supervised us to reveal the person's behavior, state of mind, the humans' condition and their interaction in the society through their characteristics and different philosophical explanations, defining the distinction of philosophical fiction and tendencies in actual literary works of some writers. Biographical approach directs us to study and analyze the authors' creative work and their contribution to the development of Contemporary American Literature with philosophical tendencies. Their works are considered the most famous and phenomenal in the sphere of Modern Literature. In this research, we applied descriptive and analytical method, formalistic conceptual and empirical method. In addition, we can apply biographical approach in investigating the novels by famous Russian and American writers. Merely we think that descriptive and analytical method in research the most effective one that suits all our aims because it includes comparative and correlational methods. Hence, in our second chapter we will analyse and compare different works for determining the main philosophical tendencies that are the main specific feature of any philosophical prose.

Results:

All in all, the above factors in their totality acted as powerful incentives for the search for a single concept of the world and man in art and literature and, therefore, entailed an inevitable retrospection, revision, and interpretation of old philosophical concepts. Antonio Gramsci, Italian philosopher and journalist, once wrote about the "pessimism of the intellect and the optimism of the will" inherent in man. The modern world is imbued with a sad mood of sharply increased wisdom. The bourgeois philosophy of the 20th century, as it turned out, failed to give a modern person, an artist, not only a perspective of the future, but primarily to explain the world.

In conclusion, we can say that philosophically inclined literature has gained its popularity, taking different directions in the post war period. Mainly, French literature provided a number of crucial existentialist works during the period of war – above all, the novels of Albert Camus, the young Sartre, and the Simone de Beauvoir – and it was in France, after all, that the existentialists' novel came into being in the late 1940's.¹⁵ However, French literature today has left existentialism behind and its philosophical

¹⁵ French existentialist prose has been analysed in E.M Yevnina's study "The modern French novel", Moscow, 1962

tendency has decreased in comparison with other European literatures. Vercors is now the most distinguished author of the philosophical tendency.

The situation is different in Anglo- Saxon countries Great Britain and the United States, which traditionally “disliked” theory. Although, the work of English and American writers became markedly more inclined towards philosophical reflection during the 1950’s – 1970’s, the literature of each country has become philosophical in its own way. ¹⁶

Discussion:

Philosophically oriented literature addresses age-old questions of metaphysics, ethics, and morality. It ponders the purpose of life, the nature of God or the universe, right versus wrong, death, time—the list goes on.

In addition, we have mentioned about the evolution preconditions for the genre of philosophically inclined literature and its main representatives. We have revealed that writing with philosophical coating has picked up its notoriety, taking distinctive headings within the post war period. Primarily, French writing given a number of vital existentialist works amid the period of war – over all, the books of Albert Camus, the youthful Sartre, and the Simone de Beauvoir – and it was in France, after all, that the existentialists novel came into being within the late 1940’s. Nevertheless, French writing nowadays has cleared out existentialism behind and its philosophical propensity has diminished in comparison with other European literary works. Vercors is presently the foremost-recognized creator of the philosophical propensity.

The circumstance is distinctive in Anglo-Saxon nation’s Incredible Britain and the Joined together States, which customarily “disliked” hypothesis. In spite of the fact that, the work of English and American scholars got to be particularly more slanted towards philosophical reflection amid the 1950’s – 1970’s, the writing of each nation has ended up philosophical in its possess way.

Conclusion:

We have discussed the notion of philosophical tendencies in literature and philosophical fiction. We have analyzed variety of definitions proposed by dictionaries, encyclopedias and the general observations of scholars of literature and philosophy.

We have investigated the main tendencies of literature with philosophical generalization. We came up to a conclusion that mainly that kind of creative works includes the literary treatment of philosophers and philosophical themes ; in addition,

¹⁶ Valentina Ivashova “On the threshold of the twenty first century”, Progress Publishers Moscow, Technological revolution and literature, p.44

the philosophical treatment of issues raised by literature . The main tendencies of philosophy are: the existence of narrative raises philosophical issues in which a creator can embody, and readers be led to imagine, fictional characters, and even fantastic creatures or technologies. The ability of the human mind to imagine, and even to experience empathy with, these fictional characters is itself revealing about the nature of the human mind. Some fiction can be thought of as a sort of a thought experiment in ethics: it describes fictional characters, their motives, their actions, and the consequences of their actions. It is in this light that some philosophers have chosen various narrative forms to teach their philosophy.

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